

resorcinol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, separately.

The experimental values of nitrogen and sulphur percentage (in II~VII) are in general agreement with the theoretical values (0.3-0.5%). Melting points, yields, visible spectral data, R_f and colour of these azo dyes are compiled in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for providing necessary facilities and one of the authors (S. S.) thanks I.C.M.R. authorities for financial assistance.

References

- FRITZ HUNZIKER and JEAN SCHMUTZ, *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 67, 64455t.
- DOMEGK, *Deut. Med. Woch.*, 1935, 61, 250.
- C. O. WILSON, O. GISVOLD, F. R. DOERGE and J. B. LIPPINOTT, "Text book of Organic Medical and Pharmaceutical Chemistry", 6th (ed.), 1971.
- S. SAHNI, R. P. TYAGI, F. S. K. BARAR and B. C. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 625.
- G. S. AVERY (Ed.), "Drug Treatment, Principles and Practice of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics", ADIS Press, Sydney, 1975, p. 184.

Search for New Antiviral Agents. Part-IV : Synthesis of 2-morpholino/diethylamino-dithiocarbamyl-methyl-benzoxazinones and corresponding 3-substituted quinazolin-4-ones

V. K. PANDEY and A. K. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow
Manuscript received 12 April 1979, revised 5 December 1980,
accepted 28 January 1981

A wide variety of sulphur containing compounds such as thiosemicarbazones¹, thioureas², phenothiazines³, thioamides⁴, thiazolinones⁵ and thiazoles⁶ have been proved to possess significant antiviral activity in the experimental animals. Further, Yoshiaka *et al*⁷ have recently established the antiviral activity of some dithiocarbamates. These observations prompted the authors to unite the quinazolone and dithiocarbamyl moieties with a view to prepare compounds with modified antiviral activity, not studied so far.

Experimental

1. Morpholino/diethylamino dithiocarbamyl acetic acids :

These have been prepared following the method of Tiwari and Pandey⁸.

2.2-Morpholino/diethylamino-dithiocarbamyl-methyl-3,1 (4H)benzoxazine-4-ones : The procedure of Sammour *et al*⁹ was followed. The compounds, thus synthesised, are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—2-MORPHOLINO/DIETHYLAMINO-DITHIOCARBAMYL-METHYL-BENZOXAZINE-4-ONES

Sl. No.	R.	m.p.	Mol. formula	Analysis Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	found
1.	Morpholino	105°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	8.69%	8.41%
2.	Diethylamino	99-100°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	9.09%	9.26%

Note : All the melting points are uncorrected. Solvent used for recrystallization was ethanol.

3.2 - Morpholino/diethylamino - dithiocarbamyl - methyl-3-(aryl-substituted), 3,1 (4H) quinazolin-4-ones : A mixture of 2-morpholino/diethylamino-dithiocarbamyl-methyl-3, 1 (4H)-benzoxazine-4-one (0.01 mole) and substituted amine (0.01 mole) in 30 ml of dry pyridine was refluxed for 6 hours under anhydrous conditions. The reaction mixture was then poured in the ice cooled water containing dil HCl. The solid product that separated out, was washed repeatedly with water and recrystallized from dil ethanol. The various compounds thus, synthesized and listed in Table 2.

Antiviral Activity :

Materials and Methods : Four compounds (compound Nos. 1, 4, 6 and 9 of Table 2) were screened for their antiviral activity against Semliki forest virus (S.F.V.) on swiss albino mice weighing 20 gm (average weight). Each test compound (100 mg/kg body weight) was added to carboxy methyl cellulose (C.M.C.) solution and injected in test mouse through intraperitoneal route in two divided doses at 24 and 48 hrs after virus infection. Ten mice were used for each test compound and ten were kept as control. The mice were then observed for 15 days for the appearance of symptoms (paralysis) and death. Protection rate (survival percentage) and

NOTES

TABLE 2—MORPHOLINO/DIETHYLAMINO-DITHIOCARBAMYL-METHYL 3-(ARYL-SUBSTITUTED)-QUINAZOLIN-4-ONES

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p.	Mol. formula	Nitrogen Analysed	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	-Morpholino	-phenyl	121-22°	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	10.59%	10.43%
2.	-Morpholino	-p-methyl phenyl	111°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	10.22%	10.51%
3.	-Morpholino	-p-methoxy phenyl	128-29°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	9.83%	10.03%
4.	-Morpholino	-methyl benzimidazolyl	82-83°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	15.52%	15.26%
5.	-Morpholino	-ethyl benzimidazolyl	187-88°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	15.05%	15.42%
6.	-Diethylamino	-phenyl	143-44°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ OS ₂	10.96%	11.16%
7.	-Diethylamino	-p-methyl phenyl	94-95°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ OS ₂	10.58%	10.39%
8.	-Diethylamino	-p-methoxy phenyl	132-33°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	10.17%	10.47%
9.	-Diethylamino	-methyl benzimidazolyl	114-15°	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ OS ₂	16.01%	16.25%
10.	-Diethylamino	-ethyl benzimidazolyl	144-45°	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₄ OS ₂	15.52%	15.71%

Note : All the melting points are uncorrected. Yield ranged from 55-60%.

mean survival time (M.S.T.) were calculated as follows :

$$\text{Survival Percentage} = \frac{\text{Survival number of animals}}{\text{Initial number of animals}} \times 100$$

$$\text{M.S.T.} = \frac{\text{Summation of time taken for each animal to die} + \text{Summation of survival time of animals not dying}}{\text{Number of animals dying} + \text{Number of animals surviving}}$$

Results

The compounds 4 and 9 were found to possess 10% antiviral activity (net protection) while rest were found inactive.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. S. S. Tewari, Head, Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, for providing necessary laboratory facilities and to Dr. B. M. Gupta, Head, Division of Virology, CDRI, Lucknow, for providing antiviral screening data. The junior author (A. K. A.) is obliged to ICMR, New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. L. THOMPSON, M. L. PRICE and S. A. MINTON, JR., *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol.*, 1951, **78**, 11.

2. A. GALOBOV, E. VELIKOVA and G. VASILEV, *Chem.otherapy*, 1977, **23**, 81 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **86**, 37513.
3. TOYOSHIMA, SHIGESHI and KANO, *et al*, *Japan kokai*, 7654, 573 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **86**, 5843.
4. A. KOJI and I. YOSHIKI, *U. S.*, 3962, 928 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **86**, 43292.
5. HARNDEN, R. MICHAEL, WRIGHT NICHOLAL and DAVID, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 611, 089 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **86**, 43693.
6. P. O. SRIVASTAVA, PICKERING and V. MICHAEL, *et al*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, **20**, 256.
7. I. YOSHIKI and A. KOJI, *Japan kokai*, 76, 139, 632, *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **86**, 150654.
8. S. S. TIWARI and V. K. PANDEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 440.
9. A. SAMMOUR, A. F. M. FALIFAHMY and MAHMOUD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 222.

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Insecticides. Part-IV : Synthesis of S-(acetyl-N-substituted phenyl amine)-arylamino-1,3,4 thiadiazoles

A. K. RAMRAKHYANI, R. S. SHUKLA and P. KUMAR
Chemistry Department, Feroze Gandhi (P.G.) College,
Rae Bareilly-229 001

Manuscript received 29 February 1980, revised 18 August 1980, accepted 5 November 1980

TWENTY substituted thiadiazoles were synthesized as possible insecticides by the condensation of chloroacetyl amine with sodium salt of various thiadiazoles.